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Proposal for a
Quantum Technology Initiative
at CERN

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Proposal for a Quantum Technology Initiative at CERN

1 Executive Summary

Quantum technologies have the potential to revolutionise science and society in the next five to ten years, but require resources that are not mainstream today. CERN can be at the forefront of this revolution, setting up collaborations within Member States, as well as international initiatives. Through such endeavours, we can work to develop new computing, detectors and communications systems, in addition to advancing knowledge of quantum systems and quantum information processing. The Quantum Technology Initiative is based on almost two years of pilot collaborations and investigations — primarily in quantum computing — related to possible applications that are core to activities in HEP.

Over the past couple of years, knowledge and technologies have evolved considerably; dedicated support for research and development in quantum technologies has become part of national and international research agendas. The time has come for CERN to engage more formally with such activities. Thanks to its role in HEP and more broadly in European and international scientific research, CERN has compelling requirements for its future instruments and infrastructures, which represent very valuable application use cases, is in a unique position to catalyse interests and investigations, and can have a long-lasting impact on applying quantum technologies to High-Energy Physics and beyond. The Organization should work with Member States and HEP experiment collaborators to assess the potential impact of such technologies on future programmes, as well as to prepare the necessary skills and resources.

The CERN Quantum Technology Initiative will define a three-year roadmap and research programme in collaboration with the HEP and quantum-technology research communities. Together, we will establish joint research, educational and training activities, set up the supporting computing infrastructure, and provide dedicated mechanisms for exchange of both knowledge and technology.

This document presents: an analysis of the motivation and opportunities related to quantum technologies; a description of the cutting-edge quantum-technology activities ongoing at CERN today; and a proposal to fund, set up, operate, and assess the impact and results of a collaborative R&D programme over the next three years.

2 Motivations and opportunities

Quantum technology is an emerging field of physics and engineering, which relies on the principles of quantum physics. It is about creating practical applications — such as quantum computing, quantum sensors, quantum cryptography, quantum simulation, quantum metrology or quantum imaging — based on properties of quantum mechanics, especially quantum entanglement, quantum superposition and quantum tunnelling.

Over the past 20 years, since their initial definition by Milburn¹, quantum technologies have made great strides: they have gone from laboratory experiments to becoming a multi-disciplinary field of research and development in science and engineering. In particular, the last five years have seen a tremendous acceleration driven by advances in quantum computing and the potential it can offer in the acceleration of complex computing problems.

Today, quantum technology is organized into four main domains of R&D and applications:

1) **Quantum computing**

Quantum effects, such as superposition and entanglement, are used to speed up certain classes of computational problems beyond the limits achievable with classical systems based on logical bits. The range of problems that can potentially be accelerated goes from optimisation or simulation to sophisticated applications of machine and deep learning.

2) **Quantum communication**

Single or entangled photons and their quantum states are used to implement provably secure communication protocols across fiber-optic networks, or quantum memory devices able to store quantum states.

3) **Quantum sensing and metrology**

The high sensitivity of coherent quantum systems is used to design new classes of sensors. Detectors ranging from instruments measuring nanoscale local information to devices relying on planetary-scale coherence can significantly improve precision and enable new measurement protocols.

4) **Quantum simulation and information processing**

Well-controlled quantum systems are used to simulate or reproduce the behaviour of different, less accessible many-body quantum phenomena, thanks to the reduction in computational complexity offered by quantum devices².

Besides these four main domains of R&D, cross-cutting areas are emerging that bring together elements of more than one domain, potentially supporting a wide range of scientific and technological applications. For example, quantum software and algorithms—or combination of quantum sensors, network software and communication protocols — can be brought together to create potentially very precise, large-scale detector systems.

¹ Gerard J. Milburn, *Schrodinger's Machines: The Quantum Technology Reshaping Everyday Life*, W H Freeman & Co. (1997)

² Richard Feynman, *Simulating physics with computers* Int. J. Theor. Phys. 21 467 (1982)

The move from devices that simply rely on quantum mechanics effects (e.g. lasers, semiconductors, imaging devices, etc.) to devices that allow manipulating and controlling those effects to perform computations or design communication protocols has recently been defined as the “second quantum revolution”³. The potential of this revolution has triggered a flurry of national and international initiatives to fund and perform scientific and technology research.

Detailed lists of high-level international initiatives are available (e.g. https://iopscience.iop.org/journal/2058-9565/page/Focus_on_quantum_science_and_technology_initiatives_around_the_world). A few significant examples of particular relevance to CERN Member States and the LHC experiments collaborations are listed below:

- Europe's Quantum Flagship initiative (<https://qt.eu/>)
- The UK National Quantum Technology Programme (<http://uknqt.epsrc.ac.uk/>)
- The German Quantum Technology Programme at Fraunhofer (<https://www.fraunhofer.de/en/research/key-strategic-initiatives/quantum-technology.html>), Helmholtz (<https://www.helmholtz.de/en/research/quantum-technologies/>) and other German centers
- The Dutch National Agenda on Quantum Technology (<http://publications.tno.nl/publication/34634709/HjelXT/TNO-2019-R11338.pdf>)
- The US National Quantum Initiative (<https://www.congress.gov/bill/115th-congress/house-bill/6227>)
- The Russia Digital Economy National Program for Quantum Technologies (<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-019-03855-z>)

A number of joint collaborations are already being created across the HEP community, such as the German-Canadian network for quantum computing, hosted by DESY and TRIUMF. CERN has in place a few pilot investigation projects with leading academic and research centers and industry. It also supports the creation of national quantum initiatives with statements of interest and direct advisory roles, as for example the US National Quantum Institutes programme.

Companies such as IBM, Google, Microsoft, D-Wave, and ATOS are setting up industry-academia networks to promote and speed up research and applications of quantum technologies. Emerging start-ups bring innovation in all aspects of quantum technologies, from quantum algorithms and software, to sensors, cryogenic technologies, and quantum repeaters.

In future, CERN's challenging scientific research programme could benefit greatly from the application of quantum technologies. For example, such technologies could play an important role in supporting the design of new sophisticated types of detectors, or in accelerating the computing workloads of the physics experiments.

³ Lars Jaeger, *The Second Quantum Revolution: From Entanglement to Quantum Computing and Other Super-Technologies*, Springer (2018)

Furthermore, the broad range of specialised technical expertise found at CERN, puts the laboratory in a unique position today to take a leading role in the development of quantum technologies in almost all of its core domains for its own programmes, but also as a general contribution to the advancement of science and technology.

To prepare for such a possibility, it is necessary for CERN to put in place a comprehensive R&D and academic collaboration programme beyond the initial best-effort explorations, covering the different needs of the Organization and the HEP community. The establishment of a **CERN Quantum Technology Initiative**, to structure and coordinate such activities with the HEP community and with the many international public and private initiatives, is therefore proposed.

3 Applications of quantum technologies within CERN’s mission

In November 2018, a first workshop on Quantum Computing in HEP was organized at CERN to assess the state of the art and share ideas and proposals for possible joint R&D activities between HEP institutes and industry⁴. Over the past two years—as a direct outcome of this—best-effort initiatives, events and joint pilot projects have been set up at CERN to explore the interest of the community in quantum technologies (in particular, quantum computing), as well as possible synergies with other scientific research domains. A more detailed description of a few notable projects and technologies is provided in the Technical Annex.

The following sections highlight the main activities and interests identified so far.

3.1 Computing

Technology to build computing devices using quantum-mechanical effects has seen a tremendous acceleration in the past few years. Quantum computing uses qubits instead of bits. These are built in a variety of ways, from ion traps and superconducting circuits to impurity spins and linear optical elements.

The advantage of quantum computers over classical devices lies in the possibility of using quantum superposition effects of n qubits to perform exponentially growing (2^n) computations in parallel. This effect makes it possible to reduce the computational complexity of certain classes of problems, such as optimisation, sampling, combinatorial or factorisation problems.

Over recent years, quantum algorithms, characterised by lower computational complexity than their classical counterparts, have been discovered. Shor’s algorithm, for example, can factor integers exponentially faster than any classical one⁵; Grover’s element search in unstructured databases exhibits quadratic speedup⁶. These algorithms require large scale fault-tolerant quantum computers, whereas today we have access to *Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum* (NISQ) hardware dominated by short coherence time (noise), small number of qubits (from a few tens up to few thousands, in the case of quantum annealers) and limited lattice connectivity (in most cases, only the nearest neighbouring qubits interact).

These limitations have sparked intense R&D towards the design and optimisation of NISQ algorithms⁷ that demonstrate quantum advantage over current hardware. Early experiments have shown promise, with projected roadmaps for practical quantum computers being revised from not less than 20 years to as close as the next 5 years.

⁴ <https://indico.cern.ch/event/719844/>

⁵ Peter W. Shor. *SIAM Journal on Computing* , 26(5):1484{1509, 1997

⁶ Lov K. Grover. *Proceedings of the Twenty-Eighth Annual ACM Symposium on Theory of Computing* , STOC 96, page 212219, New York, NY, USA, 1996

⁷ John Preskill. *Quantum computing in the nisq era and beyond*. *Quantum* , 2:79, 2018

Physical qubit roadmap for quantum computer

(Source: Quantum Technologies 2020 report, Yole Développement)

Many classes of workloads typical of high-energy physics rely on optimisation algorithms, from Monte-Carlo many-body simulations, to track reconstruction and event classification.

A special class of algorithms is represented by machine-learning (ML) and deep-learning (DL) algorithms; today, quantum machine learning (QML) is a lively research field. Quantum linear-algebra routines are faster than their classical counterparts and make up most of the computational workload in ML/DL algorithms, meaning QML models could profit from this kind of acceleration⁸. Encoding a ML model as a quantum system opens the possibility of entirely new learning patterns that could be implemented on ideal or NISQ devices⁹.

Fundamental work is done today in the HEP community and in many other scientific research and industrial domains to design efficient, robust training algorithms for different types of learning networks.

Initial pilot projects have been set up at CERN in collaboration with other HEP institutes worldwide (as part of the CERN openlab quantum-computing programme¹⁰ in the IT Department) on QML. These are developing basic prototypes of quantum versions of several algorithms, which are being evaluated by LHC experiments. The range of projects include, for example, quantum graph neural networks for track reconstructions (with METU, Caltech and DESY), quantum support vector machines for Higgs boson classification (with University of Wisconsin - ATLAS experiment and IBM), quantum machine learning for

⁸ J. Biamonte, P. Wittek, N. Pancotti, P. Rebentrost, N. Wiebe, and S. Lloyd, arXiv:1611.09347v2 [quant-ph], 2018

⁹ W. Guan, G. Perdue, A. Pesah, M. Schuld, K. Terashi, S. Vallecorsa, J.-R. Vlimant, arXiv:2005.08582v1 [quant-ph], 2020

¹⁰ <https://openlab.cern/quantum>

SuperSymmetry searches (with the University of Tokyo – IHEP), and quantum generative adversarial networks for radiation transport simulation (with CQC, EPFL and Oviedo). Anomaly detection algorithms in LHC data analysis are a promising way to enlarge the scope of new physics searches towards a model independent strategy. In this context, deep-learning solutions have been tested on a set of public benchmark data sets. These algorithms can be potentially extended to the QML techniques mentioned so far and to quantum-inspired techniques such as Tensor Networks. More details are provided in the technical annex of this document.

Although not a general-purpose type of device, universal quantum computers would greatly accelerate computations, as part of large-scale heterogeneous scientific computing infrastructures (as done today with GPUs and FPGAs), but to a much larger extent. However, much more work is necessary: not only to have reliable quantum hardware, but also to understand how classical algorithms can be efficiently adapted to run on quantum computers and to develop the necessary intermediate software stack of programming languages, compilers, optimisers, and many other software engineering tools.

The work necessary to advance the state of the art in quantum algorithms and software does not, however, require a full commitment to physical quantum devices. Efficient quantum computing simulation programs running on classical hardware of sufficient capabilities are today an excellent way to build skills, design realistic algorithms prototypes and assess trends. They are essential for understanding hardware behaviour, gate operations fidelity, correctness and scaling performance, and robustness against errors, as well as for designing error-correction strategies on NISQ devices. Classical simulation of quantum hardware is a very difficult task: its complexity scales exponentially with the number of qubits. With n qubits 2^n amplitudes are needed to describe a quantum system and the memory scales exponentially. The processing is tightly coupled and requires low-latency tools, like MPI over thousands of cores. High-performance simulators, relying on x86 architectures^{11,12} or accelerators¹³ exist; their performance has been studied on HPC clusters or cloud^{14,15}.

An effort within the HEP community to build a reliable quantum-computing simulation infrastructure, capitalising on the existing unique expertise of the community in distributed computing would allow us to assess the potential of quantum computers in HEP research, accelerating innovation and enabling the development of expertise for future applications.

Traditional high-throughput computing systems, which represent the bulk of HEP computing are not well suited for large-scale coupled computations. Purpose-designed quantum simulators and HPC systems with adequate memory and network fabric are needed to perform medium to large-scale quantum simulations. CERN can rely on its developing relationship

¹¹ G. G. Guerreschi, J. Hogaboam, F. Baruffa, et N. P. D. Sawaya, *Quantum Sci. Technol.*, vol. 5, n° 3, p. 034007, mai 2020, doi: 10.1088/2058-9565/ab8505

¹² M. Smelyanskiy, N. P. D. Sawaya, et A. Aspuru-Guzik, *arXiv:1601.07195 [quant-ph]*, mai 2016

¹³ A. Avila, A. Maron, R. Reiser, M. Pilla, et A. Yamin, *Proceedings of the 29th Annual ACM Symposium on Applied Computing - SAC '14*, Gyeongju, Republic of Korea, 2014, p. 860-865, doi: 10.1145/2554850.2554892

¹⁴ E. Pednault *et al.*, *arXiv:1710.05867 [quant-ph]*, déc. 2018, Consulté le: mai 26, 2020

¹⁵ R. LaRose, *arXiv:1801.01037 [quant-ph]*, juin 2018

with HPC providers and its existing expertise in data management and large-scale distributed computing to support quantum-simulation development activities.

Conceptual similarities between quantum computers and HEP experiments can also be exploited. In both cases, quantum objects are studied and monitored using single-particle sensors connected to a data acquisition system based on custom electronics (FPGAs and ASICs). Similar infrastructures are today evaluated to assemble large-scale QC emulators with improved computing efficiency. In recent years, the development of High-Level Synthesis (HLS) software (for example within the HLS4ML project and at the CMS experiment) has introduced the possibility of automating FPGA programming and ASICs design. This suggests the possibility of creating a software library that would allow the emulation of generic quantum circuits on FPGAs through HLS and, when paired to a hardware oriented effort on QC development, develop QC control algorithms, in a way similar to what is done at the LHC with hardware triggers.

In addition to specialised qubit technologies and software and algorithmic expertise, quantum computers also require sophisticated engineering expertise in areas such as cryogenic systems or control systems. Such expertise is part of the core skills required, for example, by CERN's accelerator complex. R&D in such areas would also represent a very valuable investment, whereby CERN's unique skills base would both contribute and advance.

3.2 *Communication*

Experiments with quantum communication devices and protocols are not new at CERN. In 2009, the Organization already took part in the SwissQuantum project, a public-private initiative to set up and operate over long periods of time a prototype quantum key distribution (QKD) layer.

Today, as part of the European Quantum Flagship initiative, a new project called openQKD¹⁶ is deploying the first nodes of a pan-European QKD network to develop and test technologies and protocol for secure communication. The CERN IT Department is currently hosting a node of the initial network mesh.

CERN plays an important role in regional and European Internet infrastructures at the physical layer. For example, it has hosted the CERN Internet eXchange Point (CIXP)¹⁷ since 1996 and it has been a driving force behind the evolution of the regional internet infrastructure. The CIXP is a founding member of the European Internet Exchange Point Association (Euro-IX).

Taking part in technology investigations and supporting the deployment and operations of future QKD networks would not only be a natural extension of CERN current functions, but would also ensure that CERN continues to play a central role in the future of European and international communication infrastructures.

¹⁶ <https://openqkd.eu/>

¹⁷ <https://cixp.net/>

3.3 Sensing and metrology

In the context of particle physics, a few areas of relevance are mainly in the context of measurement of fields (e.g. magnetic fields using SQUIDS or graphene), as well as of temporal or spatial field changes, with perhaps some further areas of applicability. Interferometric measurements sensitive to inertial forces may allow detecting (e.g. in the case of atom interferometers) magnetic or electric field gradients, accelerations (vibrations) or rotations (Sagnac effect). Potential further areas of relevance to particle physics relate to measurements of position or energy. Many quantum sensing systems rely on atomic systems, but there are several other systems that are being worked on at CERN that have the potential to be equally, if not even more, useful. The following areas, mainly explored as part of efforts at facilities like ISOLDE and the AD, while sometimes still very speculative, provide potential for compelling R&D. More details are given in the Technical Annex of this document.

1) Interferometric systems: Interferometric measurements are highly sensitive to any differential forces acting on the two branches of an interferometer. In the case of ongoing activities at CERN, beams of stable or sufficiently long-lived neutral atoms (specifically, positronium, but potentially also protonium, antiprotonic atoms or neutral radioisotopic atoms in the context of the AEGIS, ALPHA-g, GBAR and PUMA experiments at the AD, but also of precision trap experiments at ISOLDE) can be used to probe gravitational, electrical or magnetic potentials, as well as frame rotations or accelerations, with dephasing and/or phase shifting being a measure of the gradient strength.

2) Novel types of entanglement: It is also possible to extend the aforementioned systems that rely on positronium atoms. It is particularly intriguing to note that, while *two-photon entanglement* has been extremely well studied, the three-photon decay of o-Ps opens the possibility of forming and studying *three-photon entanglement* in the framework of the AEGIS and GBAR experiments. Multi-photon entanglement is a very new field; it is of particular interest as it is tied to many ideas surrounding quantum communication schemes, quantum cryptographic protocols, and fundamental tests of quantum theory.

3) Single atom/ion systems: Beams of very weakly bound antiprotonic Rydberg atoms, under development at the AD can either be investigated singly (e.g. in an interferometer) or else transported and trapped (in electric gradient traps). Such antiprotonic Rydberg atoms could evidence quantum state changes through annihilation, in contrast to Rydberg atoms of normal matter. Elementary particle, ionic and mixed-charge systems in traps are very sensitive to rotations or magnetic fields, for example. For sufficient sensitivity to compete with atomic systems, large numbers would have to be trapped, e.g. in multi-well surface (planar) traps. Such large area planar traps are being evaluated as one of the possible developments for precision measurements at the AD (for trapping of antiprotons or positrons). Single trapped electrons (that form quantized atom-like “geonium” states in a Penning trap) are exceedingly sensitive to magnetic fields via detection of their cyclotron frequency, which the ATRAP and BASE experiments, for example, have measured to very high precisions. Devices based on this technology would naturally form the basis of NMR probes.

4) Further systems (even more speculative): Position-sensitive detectors with a spatial resolution at the nanometer scale might be conceivable: a (local) quantum state change

induced by a particle passing through a 2D array of trapped and prepared atoms, positioned e.g. at the apex of (nanoscale) pyramidal “pedestals” could be visualised as a quantum state change: their state could be probed via laser (all atoms should remain dark with the exception of the transitioned atom. Even more speculatively, ultra-sensitive calorimetry—reliant on detecting energy transitions in prepared atoms that are “stimulated” / “amplified” by coherence effects through the presence of low-energy electrons or photons—might be possible. Finally, the disappearance of quantum entanglement of pairs of atoms, via state changes induced by atom-electron or atom-field interactions, could possibly enable detection of ultra-low energy radiation, similar to the detection of single microwave photons in Rydberg atoms.

3.4 *Simulation and information processing*

Richard Feynman is famously quoted for his statement that “Nature isn't classical, dammit, and if you want to make a simulation of nature, you'd better make it quantum mechanical, and by golly it's a wonderful problem, because it doesn't look so easy.” It is therefore only natural that physics and high-energy physics is considered an area where quantum devices could make a difference in simulating complex dynamic interaction or multi-body systems.

Many classes of problems used in chemistry, condensed-matter physics or high-energy physics can be simulated by means of well-controlled quantum systems. In high-energy physics quite a few possible applications have been investigated in recent years, especially in the context of gauge theories and their applications to dynamic problems (e.g. heavy ion collisions), topological problems (e.g. CP violation), or high-baryon density configurations (e.g. modelling of neutron stars).

One possible approach is to design simulation strategies that apply different techniques, a mix of classic and quantum methods, to different parts of the problems and focus the attention on those areas that are computationally intractable using standard techniques. An example of this approach is the application of quantum circuits to describe the quantum properties of parton showers as a complementary technique to more classical Markov Chain Monte Carlo methods¹⁸.

Following the call to “make [simulations of nature] quantum mechanical” is not an easy task. Fortunately, many aspects of quantum devices can be understood rigorously using tools already well established in theoretical particle physics. By bringing together theoretical and experimental expertise, CERN has a unique capability to act as a catalyst for breakthroughs in quantum technologies also capitalizing on expertise in the CERN Theory Department (CERN-TH).

One natural area of focus is to identify outstanding questions in theoretical physics that can be impacted by quantum technologies. CERN-TH has significant experience in a wide range of computationally intensive areas, including evaluation of amplitudes and phase-space integrals in perturbative QCD, calculation of non-perturbative dynamics using lattice quantum

¹⁸ C. W. Bauer, W. A.de Jong, B. Nachman, D. Provasoli, [arXiv:1904.03196v2](https://arxiv.org/abs/1904.03196v2) [hep-ph], Dec 2019

field theory and computational advances associated with the S-matrix bootstrap programme. Members of CERN-TH are thus in a good position to judge the potential impact of future quantum computations and to benchmark the prospects against the current classical computing state of the art.

For example, expertise in CERN-TH may aid in mapping quantum field theories onto quantum devices, understanding and mitigating the effects of Hilbert-space truncations, and identifying the key advantages of real-time quantum field theory calculations. This fits into a long-term aim of understanding where a quantum advantage can be expected in high-energy physics applications and exploiting such advantages to obtain efficiency gains in computing, data processing and storage.

4 Strategy to support the CERN Quantum Technology Initiative

According to the final report of the High-Level Steering Committee on the European QT flagship initiative, research in quantum technologies today requires multi-disciplinary skills, including scientific knowledge, engineering expertise, hardware design and software development. It also requires an explicit education and training effort to develop the necessary skills so that future generations of researchers can further develop the technologies, as well as helping them to understand how to apply them to their specific fields of research, be it computational chemistry or materials science, high-energy-physics or space applications.

Figure 1: Structure of the research field of quantum technologies, according to final report of the High-Level Steering Committee on the European QT flagship initiative¹⁹

Today, CERN is in a unique position to establish a comprehensive R&D, academic and knowledge-sharing initiative, capitalising on existing activities, but building the necessary expertise for the future. The following sections highlight a proposal to establish such initiative, its medium and long-term objectives and the resources needed.

4.1 Governance and organisational framework

The CERN Quantum Technology Initiative (QTI) would be built around a core of existing projects and collaborations already taking place at CERN, but would scale them up across the wider HEP community, in close collaboration with national and international initiatives in the CERN Member States or from institutes collaborating in HEP experiments. The initiative would be managed by a Project Coordinator and a core team of experts for each of the technology areas of research (computing, communication, sensing, simulation and information processing), as well as for the organisation of academic and industrial collaborations. An advisory board composed of international experts would be established to guide the management team and assess progress and impact.

The CERN QTI would be established for an initial duration of 3.5 years, including a starting set-up phase of 6 months to put in place the necessary organisational mechanism, initial collaborations, and operational channels. This would then be followed by a period of 3 years of R&D, academic collaboration programmes, and knowledge sharing and transfer. Periodic

¹⁹ H-LSC QT Flagship, Final Report, 28 June 2018, <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regexpert/index.cfm?do=groupDetail.groupDetailDoc&id=34809&no=1>

reports would be produced for the CERN management, the advisory board, and other stakeholders in order to follow progress and assess the results.

The CERN QTI, through its members and activities, is expected to take part in international initiatives and collaborations, thus implementing and actively promoting the Organization’s scientific and technological objectives and helping to keep it at the forefront of research into quantum technologies. Appropriate community channels, such as a “quantum technology forum” for example, with representatives of the Member States and dedicated technical working groups, would therefore be established to integrate the CERN QTI activities within core HEP initiatives and projects, such as the experiment collaborations, the WLCG project, or the HSF consortium.

Figure 2: The CERN Quantum Technology Initiative governance model

4.2 R&D Objectives and Expected Results

R&D Roadmap

During the first six months of the set-up phase, the CERN QTI will define—in collaboration with the community stakeholders—a detailed R&D roadmap for three years of activity. The roadmap will be published as a white paper and will be used to guide the activities of the project. Updates and revisions will be periodically produced to make sure that the roadmap remains aligned with both the needs of the HEP community and the evolution of the technologies. The following short sections describe an initial set of medium and long-term objectives and expected results.

Computing

- Formalise and extend the existing catalogue of use cases and examples of possible applications of quantum computing to HEP workflows and algorithms.
- Collect and share information about existing resources, tools, libraries, and collaborations across the community, with a special focus on simulators (e.g. IBM Qiskit, Google Cirq, Intel IQS, Amazon Braket, Strawberry Fields, $t|ket\rangle$ and more cf. <https://quantiki.org/wiki/list-qc-simulators>).
- Design and deploy a distributed infrastructure for quantum computing and simulation, based on existing distributed computing expertise, to make resources

and tools easily accessible to researchers, thus enabling investigations to be performed as part of community projects.

- Identify and coordinate access to computing resources, both for simulators and actual quantum hardware, in collaboration with other Institutes or companies. Resources can come from on-premise, cloud and HPC providers.
- Use the infrastructure to set up R&D projects to adapt or design algorithms for quantum platforms and benchmark their current and potential performance.

Sensing

- Formalise and extend the existing catalogue of use cases and examples of possible applications of quantum sensing in areas relevant to HEP.
- Establish links to similar initiatives starting up at university labs and form collaborations across the community.
- Identify particularly promising technologies, focusing on a small number of developments with potential specifically for novel applications in HEP.
- Set up common R&D projects and coordinate collaboration with other Institutes or companies to adapt or develop both the technologies themselves as well as new test systems for quantum sensing approaches and benchmark their current and potential performance.

Communication

- Formalise CERN's participation in the pan-European QKD infrastructure, providing operational and technical support.
- Identify and support pilot projects exploiting the QKD infrastructure for specific uses, in collaboration with appropriate research and industry partners

Simulation and Information Processing

- Identify possible applications of quantum simulation and quantum information processing relevant to high-energy physics, leveraging CERN's range of expertise, from formal perspectives to practical implementations in hardware and software.
- Support local projects focusing on quantum simulation and information processing. Clearly identify quantum advantages and invest in their future exploitation.
- Establish global collaborations with other institutes and companies to develop quantum capabilities in combination with the unique expertise gathered at CERN.
- Benchmark the current and potential performance of quantum simulations against state-of-the-art classical computations.

4.3 Education and Training

Given the R&D and sometimes still speculative nature of quantum technologies and its longer-term impact, a solid educational and training programme must be at the core of the initiative. The CERN QTI will implement its R&D activities as a PhD-level programme, as part of the existing CERN DOCT scheme and in collaboration with relevant academic institutes with proven expertise in the field.

Opportunities for visiting professorships and scientific associates will be provided as a means to establish a mechanism of knowledge sharing across institutes and to build expertise within the Organization.

Education and training events will be organised in collaboration with selected industry partners to speed up the establishment of a solid foundational layer of competences across the different CERN R&D and engineering activities. Proven expertise in the organisation of academia-industry training programmes is already available at CERN through projects such as CERN openlab and can be easily extended to the needs of the CERN QTI.

4.4 Collaborations and Knowledge Sharing

A critical aspect of the activities of the CERN QTI is the establishment of collaborations with existing and future quantum initiatives of CERN Member States and HEP experiments members. The broad sharing and exploitation of the knowledge produced with academia and industry through publications, joint development activities or technology licensing is also strategic to the success of the Initiative. This is not only important within the R&D programmes, but also in terms of sustainable impact beyond the HEP domain into industrial and societal activities.

Initial discussions and pilot collaborations on R&D into quantum technologies have already been established with academia and industry in CERN Member States and other HEP experiments members and can be used as a starting point for further development.

Current examples include:

- Evaluation of the quality of quantum random generator for Monte Carlo simulation with Cambridge Quantum Computing in the **United Kingdom** and Oviedo University in **Spain**
- Development of Quantum Generative Models with Aachen University and DESY in **Germany** and Cambridge Quantum Computing in the **United Kingdom**
- Design of distributed quantum computing simulation platforms with INFN-CNAF in **Italy**
- Collaboration to the creation of a *Centre for Quantum Algorithm Studies and Applications* with University of Padova in **Italy**
- Development of a Quantum Graph Neural Networks for particle tracking with Middle Eastern Technical University in **Turkey** and GluoNNet in **Switzerland**
- Hosting of quantum communication router and use cases for the openQKD projects with University of Geneva and Idée Quantique in **Switzerland**
- MECHANICS, a project proposal on Quantum Machine Learning and Quantum Computing as a Service for the EC ICT40 call with FZ Juelich and T-Systems in **Germany**, Nokia in **Finland**, OROBIX and Istituto Mario Negri in **Italy**

- Q-POWER, a project proposal on Quantum Technologies Citizen Science activities with Ludwig Boltzmann Gesellschaft in **Germany** and Aarhus University in **Denmark**
- Support and advisory participation in US National Labs proposals in the context of the US Quantum National Initiative (Oak Ridge, Fermilab)
- Development of Quantum Support Vector Machines for signal/background classification (IBM, University of Wisconsin - ATLAS, Tokyo University-IHEP)
- Quantum implementation of single layer perceptron and benchmarking of the Intel Quantum Simulator (Intel)

The CERN QTI—in direct collaboration with existing CERN structures, such as the Knowledge Transfer Group, CERN openlab, or IdeaSquare—will build and share knowledge primarily via two mechanisms:

1. **The creation of a rich network of collaborations within and outside the HEP community** by taking part in international initiatives and networks in the CERN Member States and initiatives run by institutes collaborating in HEP experiments. Areas of joint R&D and technology exploitation will also be identified outside the HEP community, in fields where quantum technologies show potential for innovative applications, such as biology, transportation, logistics, finance or engineering of quantum systems. Awareness of CERN’s specific expertise and technological capabilities will be created via the publication of value proposition documents, adapted to different audiences. Whenever appropriate, “discovery days” will be organised to identify potential areas of collaboration and exploitation of CERN technologies beyond the HEP domain into industrial and societal applications.
2. **The maximisation of dissemination and adoption of its research outcomes** by publication of research outcomes through scientific journals, but also specialised media outlets, or social-media channels. Any commercially exploitable result will be subject to appropriate IPRs, protection mechanisms (e.g. publication or patenting) and open or dual licensing frameworks. Whenever relevant unique skills are available at CERN in quantum technologies, training events, consultancy agreements will be assessed and implemented. Support will also be provided for potential spin-off creation through the existing CERN business-incubation network.

5 Glossary

NISQ	Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum: used to refer to quantum computing systems with a limited number of qubits (50-1000) not allowing effective error correction
Noise	Noise in quantum computers is due to disturbances of the environment on the system qubits that cause loss of coherence and therefore information
QKD	A method that leverages the properties of quantum mechanics, such as the no cloning theorem, to allow two people to securely agree on a key (OTP – One Time Pad). A key in this context is a secret code-word that is shared only between you and the person you are trying to communicate with. This secret code-word can then be used to encrypt messages such that they can be transmitted without being read by a malicious third party
Qubit	The fundamental unit of computation of quantum systems. Whereas a classical bit can be in two states (either zero or one), a quantum bit or qubit can be in a sort of zero state and in a one state at the same time. This situation is called a superposition of (quantum) states.
Quantum Advantage or Quantum Supremacy	For a given problem, the improvement in run time for a quantum computer versus a conventional computer running the best known conventional algorithm.
Quantum Error Correction	Quantum error correction combats the information loss due environmental disturbances in the computational state of the system by taking such state and spreading it out over an entangled state over many qubits. This entanglement allows outside classical observers to observe and remedy disturbances without observing the computational state itself, which would collapse it.
Quantum Turing Machine or Universal Quantum Computer	A Quantum Turing machine (QTM), also a universal quantum computer, is an abstract machine used to model the effect of a quantum computer. It provides a very simple model which captures all of the power of quantum computation.
Quantum Repeaters	Quantum repeaters enable long distance communication over a quantum network beyond the typical limits of an optical fiber that can transmit a qubit over roughly 100 kilometers. Quantum repeaters can be thought of as a series of short entangled links connecting the two points. The quantum information can then

	be teleported through these links and arrive safely at its destination.
Quantum Sensor	A quantum sensor is a device that exploits quantum correlations, such as quantum entanglement, to achieve a sensitivity or resolution that is better than can be achieved using only classical systems. A quantum sensor can measure the effect of the quantum state of another system on itself

Annex I

Technical Annex

1. *Quantum Computing Projects*

Quantum Optimisation of ALICE Grid Data Placement:

Quantum algorithms are being investigated for accelerating the optimisation of the storage distribution on the WLCG Grid, starting from the specific case of the ALICE Collaboration at the LHC. The aim of this project is the optimisation of storage, movement, and access patterns for the data produced by the ALICE experiment in quasi-real-time in order to improve resource allocation and usage, thus leading to increased efficiency in the broader data-handling workflow. This project was awarded one-year funding under the European Union's ATTRACT initiative. The optimisation problem has been defined in terms of Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL). This technique represents one of the most promising technologies in the field of decision-making and self-learning and it is at the core of many autonomous control systems. The DRL approach consists of different elements: environment simulation, reward mechanism and utility functions - Q-functions. The DRL framework is being implemented as a hybrid classical-quantum framework: a classical LSTM network is used to simulate the ALICE grid I/O throughput achieving 4% accuracy; the utility function is represented by the free energy of a Quantum Boltzmann Machine (QBM) [23]. The QBM training process is being implemented on a quantum annealer using the Hamiltonian of a transverse-field Ising model.

Quantum Generative Adversarial Networks:

The HEP community has been studying Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) and other deep generative models to replace traditional time-consuming Monte Carlo-based simulation obtaining very promising results. At the same time, Quantum Machine Learning has developed into a very rich research field, investigating how quantum algorithms learn from data how to perform specific tasks [17].

Quantum GAN models, such as the one presented in [18], represent an interesting example and, in our field, they are being explored for the simulation of particle showers in calorimeters, interpreted as a pixelated image. The problem is reduced into one-dimensional probability distribution represented in terms of quantum states. Two different approaches are being studied, one based on qubits, similar to the model proposed in [18] and the second based on continuous variable computing, where the basic information-processing unit is an infinite-dimensional bosonic mode and momentum - position representation is used [19].

In both cases, preliminary results prove that QGAN enables to generate targeted probability distribution effectively with high fidelity, although its convergence is still slow with respect to classical GAN and requires further optimisation in terms of networks parameters initialisation and circuit depth.

Quantum Graph Neural Networks:

Charged particle tracking in high luminosity environment will be an extremely demanding task in terms of computing resources and Deep Learning-based techniques are being investigated achieving different levels of accuracy.

The HEPtrkX project [20], in particular, represented tracking hits as space-points arranged in connected graphs and successfully developed a set of Graph Neural Networks (GNN) to perform hits and segments classification. The work in [21] represents an exploratory look at the HEPtrkX GNN architecture from a quantum computing perspective, re-implementing the GNN as a Tree Tensor Network (TTN), a hierarchical quantum classifier originally designed to represent quantum many body states described as high-order tensors [22]. In this case, the TTN consists of R_y rotations and CNOT gates, the data points are encoded as parameters of R_y rotation gates and the output is measured from a single qubit. Initial tests show that the TTN-based model converges, although the final accuracy is lower than in the classical case and further optimisation of hidden features and the number of iterations are being investigated.

Quantum support vector machines for Higgs boson classification:

Quantum support vector machines (QSVMs) are among the more stable quantum neural networks architectures [24,25]. At CERN, they are being investigated for the classification of particle collision events that produce a certain type of decay for the Higgs boson. Specifically, such networks are being used to identify instances where a Higgs boson fluctuates for a very short time into a top quark and a top anti-quark, before decaying into two photons. The QSVM performance is compared to different classical classifiers (i.e SVM or BDT) in terms of classification accuracy, but also time to convergence and training data-set size. Preliminary results, obtained using the IBM quantum simulator, show that the QSVM can achieve performances that are comparable to its classical counterpart in terms of accuracy, while being much faster. The effect of noise is now under investigation in order to understand performance on real hardware.

Quantum machine-learning for SuperSymmetry searches:

Variational Quantum Algorithms [26,27] are being studied for the classification of SuperSymmetry signals from Standard-Model background, using SuperSymmetry data set in the UCL machine-learning repository. The efforts have focused on two approaches: quantum circuit learning (QCL) and quantum variational classifiers (QVC) [28]. Performance of the quantum algorithms is measured in terms of AUC and ROC curves. Results are comparable to classical standard multi-variate classification techniques based on a boosted-decision tree and a deep neural network. The quantum variational classifier is also tested on real quantum hardware (IBM) for a relatively small size problem and results are compared to simulations. While demonstrating discrimination power, this initial experiment shows that performance varies between the simulated and real environment. The effect is probably due to noise.

2. *Quantum Sensing and Metrology Technologies at CERN*

Quantum sensors use the quantum nature of a system to detect or measure the properties of their environment, capitalizing on the central weakness of quantum systems and on their strong sensitivity to external disturbances. A review of existing and potential systems and

their applicability as quantum sensors is given in [1]. In the context of particle physics, a few areas of applicability are mainly linked to the measurement of fields (e.g. magnetic fields using SQUIDS or graphene), as well as of temporal or spatial field changes, with perhaps some further areas of applicability. Interferometric measurements sensitive to inertial forces may allow detecting (e.g. in the case of atom interferometers) magnetic or electric field gradients, accelerations (vibrations) or rotations (Sagnac effect). Potential further areas of relevance to particle physics relate to measurements of position or energy. Many quantum sensing systems rely on atomic systems, but there are several other systems that are being worked on at CERN that have the potential to be equally, if not even more, useful. In the following, several potential systems will be listed, drawing occasionally on the broad-ranging review [1], with the caveat that some ideas are very speculative.

1) Interferometric systems:

Interferometric measurements are highly sensitive to any differential forces acting on the two branches of an interferometer. In the case of ongoing activities at CERN, beams of stable or sufficiently long-lived neutral atoms (specifically, positronium, but potentially also protonium, antiprotonic atoms or neutral radioisotopic atoms) can be used to probe gravitational, electrical or magnetic potentials, as well as frame rotations or accelerations, with dephasing and/or phase shifting being a measure of the gradient strength [2].

Existing atomic systems can do this as well (specifically for gravimeters, tests of the weak equivalence principle or of the universality of free fall [3]), but positronium in particular, because of its minute mass, is particularly sensitive. While formation of a beam of meta-stable positronium has just been established, and an annihilation detector capable of reconstructing in 3D the point of annihilation of Ps will shortly be tested with a beam of Rydberg positronium (both at AEgIS), a matter or optical interferometer for such systems has yet to be built, resp. designed, and interferences detected. Gratings (silicon wafers with 1~30 micrometer slits from PSI) are being readied for a test with a matter-based interferometer. Alternatively, development of an optical grating (photo-ionizing metastable Ps or inducing a transition into para-Ps) will require currently unavailable resources, but for which the expertise is available (AEgIS). Further developments could also rely on beams of very weakly bound antiprotonic Rydberg atoms, also being developed at the AD [4].

2) Novel types of entanglement:

As an extension of the above systems relying on positronium atoms, it is particularly intriguing that while *two-photon entanglement* has been extremely well studied, the three-photon decay of o-Ps opens the possibility of forming and studying *three-photon entanglement*. Multi-photon entanglement is a very recent field, and of particular interest as it is tied to many ideas surrounding quantum communication schemes, quantum cryptographic protocols, and fundamental tests of quantum theory.

It should also be noted that there are very few sources in nature of multi-particle entanglement, nor are there many sources of entangled gamma rays. Positronium is quite unique in that regard [5]. In order to show the multi-particle entangled nature of photons from Ps

annihilation, one would need a beam of a long-lived state of Ps in the orthopositronium manifold annihilating mainly into three gammas; with a lifetime of 1.1 μs , the 2^3S state is very well suited for this. AEGIS is developing this beam and is collaborating with the authors of [5] to perform the first studies towards the study of entanglement in the polarization degree of freedom of annihilation gamma rays.

3) Single atom/ion systems:

a) Rydberg atoms and Rydberg antiprotonic atoms

Rydberg atoms, whether purely matter or also containing antimatter components, are particularly sensitive to their environment due to the potentially very large dipoles that characterize them. They have for example been employed as single-photon detectors for microwave photons. Beams of very weakly bound antiprotonic Rydberg atoms, under development at the AD can either be investigated singly (e.g. in an interferometer) or else transported and trapped (in electric gradient traps). Such antiprotonic Rydberg atoms could evidence quantum state changes through annihilation, in contrast to Rydberg atoms of normal matter (see e.g. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332085984_Quantum_sensing_using_Rydberg_atoms). Similarly, targeted annihilation of an individual antiprotonic atom from a trapped (possibly mixed matter – antimatter Rydberg atoms) and possibly entangled ensemble should be possible, thus instantaneously affecting the complete ensemble.

A hint of a possible observation in 2018 by AEGIS of the reflection of Rydberg antihydrogen atoms on gold surfaces opens the possibility of using such a system to probe surface electric fields, which is already done with positrons, and which is used to study defects, carry out porosimetry, or do surface material studies; “antihydrogen reflectometry” or “positronium reflectometry” would extend such studies to much lower energies.

b) Elementary particle, ionic and mixed-charge systems in traps

Single trapped ions are very sensitive to e.g. rotations or magnetic fields; for sufficient sensitivity to compete with atomic systems, large numbers would have to be trapped, e.g. in multi-well surface (planar) traps. Such large area planar traps are being evaluated as one of the possible developments for precision measurements at the AD (for trapping of antiprotons or positrons). Coupling such planar traps with attempts at laser cooling of anions (required for sympathetic cooling of antiprotons) opens the interesting possibility of trapped alternating charge arrays of ions, with an overall net charge of zero (in contrast to macroscopic same-charge ensembles). A similar 2D surface well array would also be suitable for trapping large numbers of (metastable) Rydberg atoms.

c) Single (anti)particles in traps

Single trapped electrons (that form quantized atom-like “geonium” states in a Penning trap) are exceedingly sensitive to magnetic fields via detection of their cyclotron frequency which e.g. the ATRAP and BASE experiments have measured to very high precisions. Devices based on this technology would naturally form the basis of NMR probes.

Alternatively, vacuum sensing of pressures below 10^{-12} mbar is exceedingly difficult with classical means, while antiproton lifetime measurements allow covering the range down to 10^{-19} mbar. Similarly, by lifetime and ‘temperature’ measurements of individual antiprotons, it is possible to detect electron fluxes far below current measurement thresholds. In a related approach, detection of ions via annihilation with trapped antiprotons allows measuring ion fluxes at exceedingly low levels.

4) Further systems (probably very far fetched):

Very speculatively, position-sensitive detectors with a spatial resolution at the nanometer scale might be conceivable: a (local) quantum state change induced by a particle passing through a 2D array of trapped and prepared atoms, positioned e.g. at the apex of (nanoscale) pyramidal “pedestals” could be visualized as a quantum state change: their state could be probed via laser (all atoms should remain dark with the exception of the transitioned atom. See e.g. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1910.10737> or <https://quantum-sensing.physik.unibas.ch/publications/research-articles.html>

Even more speculatively, ultra-sensitive calorimetry relying on detecting energy transitions in prepared atoms that are “stimulated” / “amplified” by coherence effects through the presence of low-energy electrons or photons might be possible.

Finally, the disappearance of quantum entanglement of pairs of atoms via state changes induced by atom-electron or atom-field interactions could possibly allow detecting ultra-low energy radiation, similar to the detection of single microwave photons in Rydberg atoms [6]. Specific systems, like entangled states of Ps with protonium atoms (as hydrogen-like atoms, they share the same frequencies for specific transitions), or of matter atom – antimatter atom entangled pairs, might turn out to be particularly sensitive, and more importantly, easy to detect through annihilation.

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